

**Codesigning new transformative pathways
through a social learning process**

Research Report

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Lovely people

Delicious food

**Some good
reflections**

Great meeting

Work in progress*

*Dive Deep participant [evaluating the event in 5 words]

Dive Deep and Dream Big: codesigning new transformative pathways through a social learning process

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Abstract

Despite the efforts, including from local communities and municipalities, the sustainability challenge gets harder every day. To avoid the worse and irreversible consequences of climate change, we need to cut our rising carbon emissions in half in the next few years. And that would be just the starting point. And it is not by far the only 'impossible' challenge to achieve.

We now live on the edge of chaos. New possibilities for transformation arise from existing experiments with alternative practices, new policy commitments, and a growing sense of urgency powered by climate movements. Coronavirus can also be a window of opportunity.

For the next phase of transition to happen, with the emergence of sustainable and disruptive patterns of activity, there is the need to reinforce bridging activities. Social innovation leaders need to jointly reframe their messages and strategies to navigate the new possibilities.

The 'Dive Deep & Dream Big' process started in 2019 and was set as a collaborative inquiry to support break-through change at the municipal scale. Individuals and organizations working in different contexts got together to share knowledge and develop new pathways leading to translocal empowerment.

We adopted critical participatory action research and focus on the development of spaces where renewal can be nurtured in these times of reorganization. This is expected to lead to new agreements and actions, but it is primarily designed to facilitate multi-stakeholder learning processes and open the floor for the emergence of new shared meanings. We adopted a mixed methods approach to data collection, combining qualitative interviews, participant observation, and online surveys. For evaluating results, we used a framework based on the dynamics of self-organizing, complex adaptive systems.

The central piece of the process was a 5-days meeting event in Brussels (5th-9th March 2020). Forty-seven people participated, ages 20-78, mostly coming from the United Kingdom and Belgium. The group included practitioners, people involved with knowledge, networkers and activists. Motivations were related to learning and exchanging knowledge, networking and the opportunity to set new joint forces towards transformation. Despite efforts, policymakers and the most unprivileged were absent.

The facilitation of the event was inspired by Theory U, following a sequence of deep listening of the challenges, by embodying the stories of our times; connection with deepest sources of self and will, allowing themes to emerge; co-creation in groups and open spaces; celebration and closing. As intended, it was an effective self-organized process.

Quite positive achievements were attained. First, a rich mix of catalysts, intermediaries, frontrunners, drivers and visionaries was gathered, leading to manifested satisfaction with the networking and socializing process. Social and political capital were clearly enhanced, and this can be the cornerstone for adaptive governance. Also, the learning process was supportive, allowing strong emotions to emerge through in-depth discussions, psychodrama and multi-sensory experiences. Time and space for the unexpected was allowed.

On the contrary, there was a lack of content, debates were not always properly informed with existent knowledge nor systems practice, and there was limited time to work on possible pathways. This led to an intense polarization, allowing to illuminate the 'blind spot' of transition efforts, namely the stretch between action and acknowledging trauma. Only partial catharsis and limited conciliation occurred, and no significant effort has been made to find creative responses to differences.

Based on agreements, a new narrative of change is expected to consolidate, in the border of inner and outer transition, integrating self-care, community care and global care, with cultural change as a leverage point. By balancing power and addressing privilege, it would be possible to curate places of inclusion and connection that take advantage of edges, safe zones for expression, bringing in memories from the elders and longings for the desired futures.

A proposal for a structured collaborative intervention is presented in this report, translating the narrative of change into action, hopefully capable of catalysing and supporting ambitious and inclusive systemic change at the municipal scale. The intervention is centred around renewal and connects polarities, integrates head, heart, and hands, and it is expected to allow us to move from domination to imagination.

The Dive Deep compares favourably with other projects in terms of the capacity to congregate different actors. Efforts to map tools, models and resources delivered only limited information, and the process lacked clear

agreements and proposals for action. Expectations were not fully met, even if the event was considered quite useful and even a life changing experience for many of the participants.

We believe that it is not too late for conciliation of the manifested polarization and crystallizing of a new approach to renewal at the municipal scale. Several suggestions to improve the Dive Deep process are presented, and next steps suggested. The Dive Deep inquiry is ready to go for the 'last mile'. It can also be adjusted and replicated with new actors in different contexts. The ambition is to prototype the new, exploring the future by doing, supporting communities to be creatively responsive to change and conflict.

Disclaimer

I am Consciousness itself, manifested in a white, middle age, middle class, man, born and living in Portugal, with a catholic education, facing the environmental destruction with radical acceptance while fully committed in Humanity's evolution, with an engineering mindset that makes me look for tools and ways to make things better, believing that ego transcendence is the Holy Grail, focused in community and integration, with a tendency to avoid conflict, dedicated to action-research and doing a PhD thesis on Climate Action – Synergies between citizen-led initiatives and local governments, with a governmental scholarship, mostly reading papers written in English from western researchers, European centered, working with the Transition movement, spending too much time on my computer, writing the report during the coronavirus epidemic, not fully aware of all my bias.

In the report I use the personal pronoun 'we' because, despite being the only accountable for the scientific research, the Dive Deep is a collective inquiry.

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Introduction

Dive Deep & Dream Big

The 'Dive Deep & Dream Big' process was set as a collaborative inquiry with the question: "How can we better support people to co-create and sustain ambitious and inclusive responses to the climate and ecological crisis at a municipal scale?" (*Dive Deep & Dream Big*, 2019).

The expressed intention was to gather a "rich mix of activists, practitioners, politicians and others who have the skills and capacity to explore this issue, focusing on the town/city scale" in order to "develop and participate in an experimental process, map and share our experience, knowledge, practice and perspectives, build trust, listen deeply to what's needed and stretch our understanding of what's possible" (*idem*).

The process started in June 2019, catalysed by the Transition Network and mainly funded by KR Foundation. The Transition Network supports the Transition movement, a successful grassroots innovation looking for local solutions to climate change and related societal challenges (Feola & Nunes, 2014). KR is a philanthropic foundation with the mission of addressing "the root causes of climate change and environmental degradation", investing primarily in two programs related to sustainable finance ("Keeping Fossil Fuels in the Ground") and sustainable behaviours ("Mainstreaming low-impact living") (KR, 2020).

The funder sparked the process with the intention to generate synergies between its grantees working at (trans)local level and to enlighten new paths that could potentially be presented to funders. Transition Network brought to this process its capacity to move across a wide political spectrum, the optimistic approach on consensus, and the focus on collaborative learning processes connected to emotion, place and action (McGregor & Crowther, 2016).

The Bridging Role

Several processes are happening that contribute to a convergence of ideas and efforts among different (trans)local 'sustainability' initiatives. In 2017, the 'Transformative Social Innovation Manifesto' was collaboratively produced under the impulse of an European Union funded initiative (TRANSIT, 2017). It sets principles and commitments for "new ways of doing, thinking and organizing, and aiming towards a world based on ecological and human values, nurturing the commons and treasuring basic human rights and democracy".

One of these principles is the translocal empowerment. Global networks of local initiatives are believed to "integrate the best of both the global and the local" (*idem*). To effectively countervail the current power structures, there is a call (Avelino, 2019) for more strategic collaboration between these networks (alongside the spread of new narratives). It is defended that

translocal processes represent a new form of global networked governance (Bulkeley, 2005).

ECOLISE, a unique meta-network for community-led initiatives on climate change and sustainability, was founded in 2014. In the recent collaborative status report (Penha-Lopes & Henfrey, 2019) it proposes seven steps for sustainability (in the European context), namely: moving beyond growth, nurturing commons ecologies, eco-social regeneration, solidarity economics, inclusive governance, transformative social innovation and enabling community-led action.

In order to support community-led action, the report advocates for suitable legislation, awareness activities, technical assistance, comprehensive funding and opening of policy development processes (*idem*). It also tries to make visible the results from several research projects, like ARTS, PATHWAYS and TESS, that studied the governance implications of transcending the local level. These studies identify as major barriers social acceptance and resistance from incumbent regimes (Hof et al., 2016). They advocate for supporting “network hubs that integrate or moderate between local initiatives and are led by experienced and well-networked managers” (*idem*).

Similar conclusions arrived from the ‘Municipalities in Transition’ project. Perceived barriers to scaling were rules, culture (narratives) and political environment (polarization) (Macedo, 2019). It was suggested to “connect people from the ground talking from the open heart and technicals to ‘translate’ these needs to policy recommendations” (*idem*).

In order to nurture renewal in these times of reorganization, the adaptive governance theory calls for policies that can support comanagement efforts and emphasis the role of ‘bridging organizations’, together with key persons that might provide the necessary leadership, trust, vision and meaning (Folke, Hahn, Olsson, & Norberg, 2005). These bridging organizations connect local actors and communities with other scales of organizations, bring resources and mobilize knowledge and social memory (*idem*). They are critical for the social learning process (Berkes, 2009) and are similar to the concept of ‘boundary organizations’ (Cash, 2000).

In the transition management framework, the bridging role is played by the ‘transition arena’, “bringing a small number of societal forward-thinkers to a new, shared perspective on a complex social issue and to a common path towards finding a solution” (van Buuren & Loorbach, 2009). The bridging efforts are expected to facilitate the re-alignment and the re-institutionalisation of the sociotechnical regime (Geels & Schot, 2007), allowing the articulation of new directions of societal change (Rosenbloom, 2017). These pathways are expected to allow us to stay within a safe operating space and to meet ambitious sustainable development goals (Leach et al., 2012).

Several initiatives are dedicated to documenting possibilities and envisioning positive futures. Some good examples include ‘Seeds of Good

Anthropocenes' (Bennett et al., 2016), the Great Transition Initiative (Tellus Institute, 2019) or the Project Drawdown (Drawdown, 2019). Future Earth is one of the most significant global networks connecting researchers and practitioners (Future Earth, 2019). Michael Narberhaus, founder of the Smart CSOs Lab, stresses the need to spread "stories about a larger us", avoiding the collapse, oppression and the enemy narratives (Michael Narberhaus, 2019). He defends a transversal movement away from ideologies and capable of embracing a diversity of worldviews (*idem*).

The Global Challenge

Satisfying basic needs without compromising the supporting environment is a crude but simultaneously universal and critical preliminary criteria for any species survival. Recent studies show that no country has yet found the formula to meet its citizens' basic needs within the planetary limits on resources' use (O'Neill, Fanning, Lamb, & Steinberger, 2018). The 'safe and just space for humanity' (Raworth, 2012) remains as no more than a dreamland.

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development was approved in 2015 by the United Nations Member States. After four years, the first official report acknowledges that we are not on track to achieve most of the goals (Independent Group of Scientists appointed by the Secretary-General, 2019). Of all the negative trends, four are considered particularly worrying: rising inequality, climate change, biodiversity loss and waste generation.

The accelerating climate change is the most paradigmatic symptom of our unsustainability. It is a consequence of nearly every human activity and produces negative impacts in most of human and natural systems (some extending for millennia). Many now advocate that it is already impossible to avoid a near term social collapse (Bendell, 2018). The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2018) suggests that it is still possible to prevent the most catastrophic impacts, but only if we produce a wide, immediate, fast and unprecedented societal transformation (Figure 1). Scientists all over the world repeat warnings on climate emergency (Ripple, Wolf, Newsome, Barnard, & Moomaw, 2019).

Figure 1 – Mitigation pathways consistent with limiting warming to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels.

Some promising responses to the climate challenge are already visible, coming from governments at all levels, grassroots initiatives, the legal system or businesses (*idem*). These efforts are expected to thrive in a context of eroded trust in institutions and democracy (Foa, Klassen, Slade, Rand, & Collins, 2020), severe polarization (Carothers & O’Donohue, 2019) and mainstreamed extremism (Davey & Ebner, 2019), pervasive injustices and inequalities (Agyeman, Bullard, & Evans, 2002; Terry, 2009), environmental melancholia (Lertzman, 2015), social unrest (Dardeli, 2020) and information disorder (Lazer et al., 2018).

Besides ecological collapse (together with the scarcity of resources), other mutually reinforcing risks contribute to our unprecedented existential crisis, namely nuclear war and technological disruption (Harari, 2018). Still, the myth of a Noah’s Ark still persist, precluding transformative action from political and business elites (Harari, 2016). There is the need to navigate between dystopian visions of environmental and societal collapse and overly optimistic utopias that support ‘business-as usual’ (Bennett et al., 2016).

The Local Call

All around the world, local communities decided to face the global challenge. Transition initiatives, permaculture, ecovillages, energy or food cooperatives, alternative currencies, alongside many other forms of activism, are now “envisioning, creating and living within alternatives that are rooted in fundamental ethical commitments to sustainability, equality and social justice” (Penha-Lopes & Henfrey, 2019, p. 107). They thrive in messy and fertile social contexts (Sekulova, Anguelovski, Argüelles, & Conill, 2017).

Local governments equally promote policy innovations towards sustainability. Following Local Agenda 21 initiatives (Pinto, Macedo, Macedo, Almeida, & Silva, 2015), they now put effort in localising the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals and in promoting low carbon communities (EEA, 2016). Often, they also organize in networks, like ICLEI, Covenant of Mayors, C40 or Resilient Cities (Climate Chance, 2019, pp. 56–57). A new municipalism movement is also rising, namely since the Fearless Cities Summit in Barcelona in 2017 (Russell, 2019) - the municipal scale (from small villages to metropolitan boroughs or city-regions) is considered strategic for transformative politics.

These local efforts, while significant in numbers (e.g. Reckien et al., 2018), are apparently getting fragmented (Hodson & Marvin, 2017) and face difficulties in materializing transformation due to issues like the rebound effect (Ruiz-campillo, 2020). Many tensions and obstacles to partnership still persist and results are far from meaningful (Macedo, Huertas, et al., 2020). Transformation arising from local action is believed to benefit from long-term agendas and networks (Amundsen, Hovelsrud, Aall, Karlsson, & Westskog, 2018), namely the already mentioned bridging efforts. The 'Municipalities in Transition' project is a paradigmatic answer to this challenge since it was started to develop a framework that could facilitate collaborative transformation at local level (MiT, 2018).

Going Glocal

The local answer to the global challenge is “far from realising their potential as catalysts for society-wide transformation” (Penha-Lopes & Henfrey, 2019, p. 108). This might be a consequence of powerful lock-ins and path dependencies only potentially overcome by bold institutional change, which, in democratic societies, require in turn a strong political mandate supported in manifested social change (Unruh, 2002).

New opportunities for transformation arise therefore from the strengthening of climate movements like 'Fridays for Future' ("Fridays For Future," n.d.) or 'Extinction Rebellion' ("Extinction Rebellion," 2019). Equally encouraged by the visible, rising and dramatic disruption in natural and social systems (Harvey, 2019), the wide necessary consensus for bold policy action is looking closer (United Nations, 2019). Meanwhile, at local, national and global level, multiple initiatives create “democratic surplus” with instruments like citizens' assemblies (Carson, 2008; Dryzek, Bächtiger, & Milewicz, 2011). We might have already achieved a social tipping point (Centola, Becker, Brackbill, & Baronchelli, 2018; Hopkins, 2019b) and could be experiencing a quantum leap (O'Brien, 2016). Coronavirus opened new windows of opportunity (Macedo, Santos, Pedersen, & Penha-Lopes, 2020).

Local sustainability action now faces the opportunity to finally become mainstream and expand globally (“going glocal”, as we call it), taking its rightful space in a polycentric and networked governance system (Ostrom, 2010; Tosun & Schoenefeld, 2017). Fuelled by social movements like feminism, cooperativism or degrowth, a democratic transformation of the

local state and economy might be emerging (Thompson, 2020). But, even with an optimistic perspective like this, the question remains: how to support and scale this work with the speed necessary to face the immense global challenge in a meaningful way, inducing systemic change?

Several strategies have been proposed and can be categorized as scaling up ("impacting laws and policy"), scaling out ("impacting greater numbers") and scaling deep ("impacting cultural roots") (Moore, Riddell, & Vocisano, 2015). The alignment of old and new ways of thinking, doing and organising can lead to new governance patterns that accelerate systemic change (Gorissen, Spira, Meynaerts, Valkering, & Frantzeskaki, 2018).

Social innovation leaders might need to reframe their messages and strategies in order to navigate the new possibilities. Namely, it is argued that properly communicating the role of local action in the context of global networked governance should be a priority (Tosun & Schoenefeld, 2017).

"Think global, act local" was used as a *motto* and still applies. We need to keep considering the global issues and find solutions that can be applied in our local communities. Nevertheless, we advocate that now is also time to carefully consider the (new) challenges to local action ("think local") and translate it to needed (policy) actions at global level that can inform a favourable institutional change ("act global"). We should also recognize that both these processes are closely interdependent.

We will now present the research and Dive Deep process, followed by results, discussion (focusing on prospects) and conclusions.

The research

Extensive and useful research has been produced in the fields of deliberate transformation (O'Brien, 2012). However, it is argued that pathways explored so far, to be 'actionable' and catalyze the necessary change, need to fully integrate political concerns and processes, moving away from 'politics-as-usual' approaches (Eisenhauer, 2016). Co-learning and co-production of solutions is advocated as a necessary explorative method (*idem*).

Research also needs to incorporate recent developments, as previously argued, including the accelerating global challenges and social responses. Previous research points out that "the challenging question remains how in contexts where the alternative practices, a sense of urgency, and policy commitment are present, a next phase of transitions can take place" (Hof et al., 2016).

The present research tries to fill these knowledge gaps. It proposes that necessary transformation can be supported through the process of catalyzing local climate action with an ambitious and inclusive agenda. We try to incorporate the scale of change that is needed and the emerging opportunities arising from climate movements.

A distinctive feature of the research might also be a focus on the 'governance challenge', avoiding the dominance of economical and psychological approaches when discussing the intended shift in lifestyles and patterns of consumption (Shove, 2010). Still, the intention is to open the floor for emergence in the intended explorative and reflexive research. Following Eisenhauer's argument, to reinforce collective change, we "must make more room for uncertainty, surprise, and politics" (2016).

The public sphere

We adopt a method of critical participatory action research, addressed at creating the conditions to participants, at individual and collective levels, "to transform the conducts and consequences of their practice to meet the needs of changing times and circumstances" (Kemmis, McTaggart, & Nixon, 2014).

Research is based in the development of a self-constituted, voluntary and autonomous 'public sphere' (*idem*) to address the concerns and issues already mentioned, namely jointly exploring the challenge of "better support people to co-create and sustain ambitious and inclusive responses to the climate and ecological crisis at the municipal scale".

This process is expected to play a bridging role, catalyzing "communication across the panarchy of institutions and ecosystems", acting as a small think-tank or forum that could provide some agreement and new ideas on this contentious challenge (Garmestani, Allen, & Cabezas, 2008).

As mentioned in the introduction, the process was mainly funded by KR Foundation and facilitated by the Transition Network. Several organizations came on board, including Anthropocene Actions, Bioregional, C40, cE3c/University of Lisbon, CTRLShift, ECOLISE, Forum for the Future, Happy Museum project, Hum, Municipalities in Transition project, New Weather Institute, Permacultura Íbera, Permaculture Association, Rapid Transition Alliance, Red de Transición, Resilience Earth, Transition Network, Transition Scotland and Université du Nous.

Process, questions and methods

A 'Dive Deep' process was initially designed for a period of nine months, from July 2019 to March 2020, later extended until July 2020. The assumed goals were:

- To map ongoing initiatives and pool resources relating local efforts for systemic transformation;
- To look for synergies between these efforts that could catalyze and explore new ways to respond to the urgent needs and opportunities that are currently emerging.

The central piece of the process was a 5-days meeting event in Brussels (5th-9th March 2020¹). Around 80 people were expected to participate, and efforts were made to maximize inclusion and diversity of interests, backgrounds, experience and geographies.

There was the purpose to work with emergence, so no concrete outputs or outcomes were expected in advance of the meeting. An implementation phase would follow.

During the 'Dive Deep' process, and using holacracy, sociocracy (Bockelbrink, Priest, & David, 2018) and similar governance approaches², several roles and circles were created for organizational purposes, including a core group, an invitation circle, a communication & communities circle, a logistics & care circle, a design & facilitation circle and a mapping & tools circle. The author of this report plays the role of embedded researcher, mostly observing but also actively supporting and participating in the process.

Specific research questions are:

- What are the motivations and expectations of people participating in the process? (see page 19 and following)
- What kind of results were obtained? (see page 34 and following)

¹ Initial dates: 22nd-26th November 2019

² The mentioned governance approaches distribute authority and decision-making throughout an organization, defining people not by hierarchy and titles, but by roles (Robertson, 2015)

- How these results contribute to catalyse society-wide transformation towards sustainability and democracy, particularly in promoting ‘glocal governance’³? (see page 44 and following)

For evaluating results, we used a framework based on the dynamics of self-organizing, complex adaptive systems (Innes & Booher, 1999) (Table 1). According to this framework, the process is “not only about producing agreements and plans but also about experimentation, learning, change, and building shared meaning” (*idem*).

Table 1 – Criteria for evaluating results (Innes & Booher, 1999).

Process Criteria	Outcome Criteria
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Includes representatives of all relevant and significantly different interests. • Is driven by a purpose and task that are real, practical, and shared by the group. • Is self-organizing, allowing participants to decide on ground rules, objectives, tasks, working groups, and discussion topics. • Engages participants, keeping them at the table, interested, and learning through in-depth discussion, drama, humor, and informal interaction. • Encourages challenges to the status quo and fosters creative thinking. • Incorporates high-quality information of many types and assures agreement on its meaning. • Seeks consensus only after discussions have fully explored the issues and interests and significant effort has been made to find creative responses to differences. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produces a high-quality agreement. • Ends stalemate. • Compares favorably with other planning methods in terms of costs and benefits. • Produces creative ideas. • Results in learning and change in and beyond the group. • Creates social and political capital. • Produces information that stakeholders understand and accept. • Sets in motion a cascade of changes in attitudes, behaviors and actions, spinoff partnerships, and new practices or institutions. • Results in institutions and practices that are flexible and networked, permitting the community to be more creatively responsive to change and conflict.

Besides active participation and observation of the process (Jorgensen, 2015; Spradley, 1980), research methods included (often informal) qualitative interviews conducted before, during and after the event, and questionnaires to participants (also before and after the event). Collected ethnographic data (fieldnotes, pictures, videos, posters, minutes of meetings and group work, answers to questionnaires and interviews...) was analyzed using qualitative content analysis (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005) and grounded theory techniques (Strauss & Corbin, 1994), in an inductive

³ “conditions under which the unsustainable regimes are discouraged and emerging sustainability transitions accelerated” (Loorbach & Lijnis Huffenreuter, 2013)

approach to take note of patterns, singularities and connections and formulate possible answers to the inquiry and related research questions.

Interim research findings were presented to participants after the event for critique and reflection. Feedback was used to refine the synthesis of the final results.

Scientific outputs from research are:

- Initial document assessing action-research on this field and methodological insights (the opening version of this report - 09/10/2019);
- Scientific report presenting and discussing the 'Dive Deep' experiment (preliminary version in April 2020 - current final version as this report);
- Presentation of a full paper in IST2020, the 11th International Sustainability Transition conference that took place in 18th-21st August 2020 (Macedo, 2020);
- A hopefully cocreated research paper to be published in a journal (to be submitted in early 2021).

We will now focus in presenting the inquiry process in more detail, namely describing what happened and who participated and why. We also present additional insights from the evaluation survey.

The process

We start by trying to answer our first research question, namely: “what are the motivations and expectations of people participating in the process?”.

Who was there? Why?

Forty-seven people participated in the Dive Deep event in 5th-9th March 2020 (see annex). They mostly came from the United Kingdom (19; 40%) and Belgium (14; 30%) (Figure 2). Ages ranged from 20 to 78 years old and there was a majority of female participants (29; 62%). The event took place in Brussels, in ‘See U’, a large temporary occupation with social and sustainable innovation, learning and experimentation purpose (former military installation).

Figure 2 – Participants’ country of residence.

Most of the participants had multiple and diverse occupations and strong commitments with sustainability transitions. Around one third (17) could be considered practitioners, mostly working with the Transition Movement in Belgium, Hungary or UK and within the project Municipalities in Transition. These also included connections to permaculture, climate action, and people working in the private and cooperative sectors. Occupations were diverse and included shamanic celebrations, ecopsychology or supporting museums.

Another third of the participants (14) were connected predominantly to knowledge, mostly working as (action) researchers, educators, trainers, consultants and also facilitators, within universities, cooperatives or informal groups. These included producing documentaries and writing

books. Topics included mindfulness, energy transitions, social justice, resilience, democracy and issues related to power and grief.

Networking and scaling sustainability frameworks were also the major calling for a significant group of people (10), including coordinators from Transition Network, C40 cities, Bioregional (One Planet Living) and Forum for the Future.

Many of the participants' activities also included some kind of activism on climate and social justice. This was the main occupation for some (5, with younger ages) working with XR, community groups and the citizen lobby La Bascule.

While around half of the participants were already working with municipalities, one was actually working in a municipality in charge of ecological transition and citizen innovation.

When asked about how they expected to benefit from the event⁴, participants primarily mentioned the opportunity for learning and exchanging knowledge:

"Learn from others and share what we know", "Learn from examples elsewhere, including case studies / stories we can use to connect more with municipalities where we are", "... increase the impact of my work both through widening and cross-fertilization of my perspectives and ideas" (...)

Secondary topics (mentioned by half of the participants) included networking:

"meeting other shift makers, finding projects I may be supportive to", "connections", "collaborative networking opportunities. This is of specific import to a study such as mine, which while being locally focused, must at the same time take a systemic view as energy systems have international networks and consequences" (...)

And also, the opportunity to set new joint efforts towards transformation:

"To leave with clear pathways for action at the municipal scale, with a stack of tools and resources, and new people to work with.", "potentially to help support/be part of some new/emergent thinking", "creating new ideas for social change" (...)

⁴ Qualitative data from the application form (open-ended question), with thematic analysis and a compilation of citations from participants' answers

Related to this, the opportunity for bridging and convergence was emphasized:

“Deepened knowledge on how to build bridges across movements”, “alignment” (...)

Other relevant expectations included inspiration:

“Coming away with some (surprising) connections or ideas to challenge and inspire my ongoing work” (...)

And personal development:

“Opening my mind and conscious” (...)

The prospect of having enough time for a deep reflection was underlined:

“It’s a bit like breathing in, and breathing out. The chance to think together is like a deep breath. We need one every once in a while, to calm our blood, create focus, dump distracting details. It’s time to reflect. Personally, I need this, though if I’m honest at a local level few other people see the need for this. So I carry the story, and this helps me rethink it, hone it and keep on track. Sounds a bit selfish perhaps, but it’s a useful role, a difficult one to hold, and needs nourishing sometimes.”

What happened?

Preparation

Regular organizational meetings and consultations (a support group was created) were held starting June 2019. In August 2019 the final location for the event was decided, considering the ease for travelling and the concentration of diverse initiatives. Initial dates for the event (November 2019) were postponed mostly due to the difficulty in dealing with the organizational demands. These initial dates were used for an in-person gathering of the group directly involved in the preparation.

Initial invitations were sent in October 2020, primarily through a ‘cascading’ process starting from the people and organizations involved. Around 100 applications were collected in this first phase and the process reopened in February 2020, additionally gathering 28 applications. A digital platform on ‘conferize’ was used for communication purposes⁵.

Two on-line meetings were organized with participants in advance of the gathering (24th and 26th February 2020).

Mapping

One of the intentions of the Dive Deep process was to “support participants in the Deep Dive inquiry to identify, share and understand what relevant tools, models, resources are available to us and share them more effectively with those who could benefit beyond the inquiry”. Overlap and potential synergies with other ongoing initiatives were discussed, namely the wiki from the European Union funded project UrbanA (Urban Arenas for Sustainable and Just Cities)⁶ and the ECOLISE wiki⁷.

The ‘mapping & tools circle’ suggested to collect stories (before, during and after the event), focusing on “personal accounts of experiences of using particular tools and methods, including experience, outcomes and reflection”. A call for contributions was sent four days before the event and four stories were collected and shared in the event itself.

Other mapping activities were promoted in the event.

The event

The inquiry process held during the 5 days event is represented in Figure 3. Concepts used to name the sequential phases come from the Theory U (Scharmer, 2009), that was used as an inspiration for the facilitation process. The process was cocreated and supported by a group of 7 experienced facilitators (see annex).

⁵ <https://www.conferize.com/divedeepdreambig/event>

⁶ <https://urban-arena.eu/sustainablejustcities-wiki/>

⁷ <http://wiki.ecolise.eu>

Figure 3 – Unfolding the inquiry (the dash line represents a critical moment happening on day 4).

On Day 1, the initial welcoming stage included framing the inquiry (Figure 4), individually and collectively acknowledging the persons and organizations that allowed the group to be there, presenting the program (“the flow/water that will carry us through”), setting group agreements, establishing ‘home groups’ and a mapping exercise.

Figure 4 – The inquiry question, made visible in the meeting room.

'Home groups' clustered participants and were meant to support the cocreation process (read more on this in page 37). They were based on the '8 shields' mentoring model (Young, Haas, & McGown, 2008) integrating learnings from natural processes and intended to rebuild "nature-connected, intergenerational mentoring communities" (8 Shields Institute, 2020). Each 'shield' corresponds to a specific energetic archetype and is associated to a person's journey through life, a time of day, season of the year and a cardinal direction, being used as metaphors for patterns on the learning process.

The 'mapping' exercise followed the principles of sociometry (Moreno, 1953) and was intended to facilitate the process of group building and to support participants' awareness of differences and relations among the group. The diversity of cultures and roles was discussed.

Several frameworks were then presented and debated, including the iceberg model to support systemic thinking (Figure 5) and 'four quadrants' from integral theory (Wilber, 2005), namely the distinction between inner and outer transition. The regeneration model (Reed, 2007) was used to contextualize different 'stories of our times', namely 'renewal', 'greenwash', 'extractive/oppression' and 'breakdown/chaos' (in a sequence from regenerating to degenerating systems, with growing needs of energy).

Figure 5 – The iceberg model (original by Peter Senge, adapted by Resilience Earth).

These stories were explored by different groups of participants, challenged to actively embody the related constellation of archetypes (Scategni, 2005). After the dramatization, those who have played roles (that included non-human beings and future generations) and watched the scene were invited to express their emotions and insights.

The end of Day 1 was used to share feelings:

“Happily dancing with roles and models”, “Déjà vu but confident”, “Deeper, deeper, deeper”, “Happy to be with people that think they don’t have all the answers” (...)

Day 2 started with a guided meditation to recall the experiences from the previous day. Feelings and intentions were shared between participants and an energizer was played. Similar moments were performed during all extent of the event and most of them will not be mentioned here for the sake of simplicity. However, we should emphasize their critical role in supporting the learning process and the distinctiveness relating ‘business-as-usual’ events.

The second day was devoted to deepening the connection with the overlying inquiry and each other’s work. A sequence of activities was facilitated for “*setting the agenda*” for the Dive Deep process:

1. Guided meditation recalling the roots and purpose of our work, the sources of energy and inspiration;
2. Sharing unfiltered thoughts (“*happy stories*”, “*how do we slow down?*”, “*allow ourselves to dream*”; “*acknowledgement of trauma*”...);
3. Individually suggesting DEEP topics (Figure 6);
4. Thematic clustering (Figure 7);
5. Group discussions.

Figure 6 – Setting the Dive Deep agenda: criteria for the topics to be discussed.

Figure 7 – Themes set for the discussion.

The rest of Day 2 was dedicated for sharing knowledge between participants, namely through short presentations and workshops⁸.

The morning of Day 3 was mostly used for group work (Figure 8). Dynamics and activities were diverse and ranged from livable debates to psychodrama. The group on “processes, strategies and models” was the greatest in numbers and went through processes of division and coalesce. After lunch each group presented their work and connections between themes were briefly discussed. A ceremony closed the day, exploring items to let go and let in.

⁸ Future Leeds Climate Hub; Dive Deep Research; Global Sustainable futures: Progress through partnerships; The Role of the School System in Perpetuating the Old Paradigm; Municipalities in Transition; Resilience cycle; One Planet Living; Qi Gong; Deeper democracy; Food Journey.

Figure 8 – Thematic group work (day 3).

Day 4 was expected to support integration and convergence of ideas, grounded on the inquiry questions, and followed by an exploration of possibilities using 'open space technology' (Owen, 2008), ending in celebration.

Instead, and following a call on feedback, a polarization started to become clear pointing to differentiated needs from participants. Some manifested requests for more practicality and deeper discussions of content, while other wanted to deepen the process, exploring emotions and truly facing power imbalances and the scale of emergency.

This polarization was further explored through a mapping exercise and a 'council'⁹, and included moments of vibrant manifestation of emotions (e.g. some participants were crying, and hugging, manifesting feelings of grief and solidarity related to environmental destruction and intergenerational injustice). Limited conciliation took place.

⁹ Sharing circle talking from the heart.

Some of the many thoughts and feeling shared included:

*“Angry and grief for not exploring the inquiry question”,
“We need to express emotions but not get drawn on them”,
“We are just tiptoeing around strong emotions”, “Do we
need to ‘explode’ the process?”, “Trusting the process,
because we are hearing our different needs”, “Enjoying the
process and knowing that there are no ‘solutions’”, “How to
reconcile organizational culture and the spaces where ‘truth’
happens?” (...)*

This moment can be considered a ‘critical turning point’ in the event (Figure 3) and will be discussed in the next chapter (The explosion, page 41).

The planned ‘open space’ then happened, with group discussions on:

- New engagement strategies (including films and global citizens assemblies);
- Places for creativity (bringing memories and imagination forward);
- Collaboration at municipal level (mapping frameworks and strategies);
- Inclusivity and regeneration (connecting polarities and keeping power in place).

The intense Day 4 ended with informal celebration, including sharing written messages, open bar, lively music performed by several participants, dance and relaxation.

The last day was used for further group work (Figure 9), with coalesce around two themes, namely:

- Integration and connection between polarities (facing the complexity of our relationships, discussing inner shadows and how to raise from our shame);
- ‘Change pirates’ (acknowledging the ecology of movements and getting beyond competition, having imagination run wild, creating roadmaps for facing climate emergency, setting next steps).

Figure 9 – ‘Open space’ discussion on day 5.

Finally, groups shared their learnings, some next steps were discussed, the journey was recalled through meditation, gratitude was manifested showing appreciation non-verbally and closing done (including each participant sharing three words to reflect his experience).

Evaluation

To support the learnings, a post-event on-line survey was prepared, and 23 responses were collected from participants, largely in the week that followed the meeting. The facilitation team met to discuss the information collected and their own impressions.

When asked about what well for them¹⁰, most people (> 80%) mentioned the networking and socializing process:

“Meeting lots of interesting people that I want to stay in contact with and maybe work with in the future.” (...)

The (facilitated) process was also largely cited (> 60%) as being responsible for the positive experience:

“The kindness of the facilitators, who were open and thoughtful in their responses” (...)

Several topics were mentioned related to *“the possibility to include deeper truth and feelings with action”* and the opportunity for self-development (*“personally reflective and deeply valuable”, “a decision to dive deep within myself rather than outside of myself”*). The venue and logistics were also referred (8; 35%).

¹⁰ Qualitative data from the evaluation form (open-ended question), with thematic analysis and citations from participants’ answers

When asked about what surprised them, responses were quite diverse and often divergent. Around one third mentioned topics related to the (deep) emotions that surfaced and were debated:

“Food Journey, Ceremony, Constellations!! That so many deep emotions came out in the group”, “I had no idea that we would get to a place of talking about grief and loss and challenging the dominant culture in such a way” (...)

We also questioned the participants relating what “stretched/challenged” them. Around 2/3 of the participants mentioned process related aspects, manifesting varied and often contrasting perspectives, that will be explored in the results’ section. The following statement captures this complexity:

“The stretch between action and acknowledging trauma... (...) was there enough stretch? how to accommodate very different cultures - people wanting stretch around content; people wanting stretch around emotional journey; people wanting stretch around modes of exploring, and those for whom the stretch is too much and bounces them out.”

The jumble of intense experiences is visible when different responses are compared, but quite frequently also within individual answers. When asked to summarize the experience in five words, one of the participants wrote what hopefully was a progressive journey:

“Frustrating alienating reengaging rewarding rich”.

However, even if the extremes of feeling frustrated or rewarded are both abundant, the most represented theme in the ‘word cloud’ is by far about connections (which is coherent with the importance given to the networking process in assessing what went well).

When asked to rate different aspects of the event (Figure 10), once more “networking & engagement” stands out as positive (just overtaken by the food journey evening).

Figure 10 – Evaluation by participants of different aspects related to the event (ratings from 1 = unsatisfactory to 5 = excellent).

Overall organization is evaluated as positive, while the venue’s appraisal seems to be quite a contentious issue. The programme, even if rated as positive, is the aspect with lower general evaluation.

Expectations were not fully met, even the event was considered quite useful and even a life changing experience for many (Figure 11).

Figure 11 – Evaluation by participants of the “knowledge, information, contacts & insights gained” (multiple choice).

Maybe this comment that was added to this specific question can capture the complexity of the impact:

“My expectations were different - I imagined a more structured, practically oriented journey. I am very happy with how it turned out though! it felt like it spoke to me in ways I don't really understand. the challenges we approached are profoundly relevant to my work in conflict and the insights will be so useful. feeling teary as I write this. incredibly grateful and devastated.”

Results

We will now focus on discussing the results that came from the Dive Deep process so far, namely relating the Brussels' gathering. This analysis is expected to allow us to answer our research questions relating results and impacts.

According to our methodology of evaluation (Table 1, page 17), we will start by using the process criteria and then the outcome criteria.

Who was missing?

The first process criterion is about the inclusion of “representatives of all relevant and significantly different interests”. Including as many stakeholders as possible is believed to lead to a more satisfactory and just process and one that serves the common good (Innes & Booher, 1999). Nonetheless, sustainability initiatives are not necessarily hindered by the absence of certain actors (Hauck et al., 2020).

The intention was to gather a “rich mix of activists, practitioners, politicians and others who have the skills and capacity to explore this issue, focusing on the town/city scale” (*Dive Deep & Dream Big*, 2019). We can thus conclude that the process was intended to mobilize front-runners committed to sustainability efforts at local level.

Looking to the presented results, we can conclude that there was some heterogeneity in terms of gender and age groups. In geographical terms there is an evident concentration on two countries (UK and Belgium), accounting for 70% of the participants, leaving Southern and especially Eastern Europe underrepresented¹¹.

In terms of backgrounds and occupations, there was a clear lack of city officers and politicians¹² and the European Union institutions were not represented. The intention of having funders present was also not fulfilled. Media, the private and the technology sectors were underrepresented, and organizations like impact hubs and social innovation labs as well.

The Transition movement had a clear dominance, with almost 2/3 of the participants having concrete connections to it. This was probably a consequence of the insufficient distributed organizational efforts in terms of disseminating the call and explains the greater numbers of people coming

¹¹ Even if not exclusive, the process is focused on the European continent. However, looking at nationalities and ethnic backgrounds, we could conclude that all Continents were represented.

¹² The coronavirus outbreak can be partially accounted for this fact (several representatives from local and regional administrations were confirmed but decided to cancel). Organizations like ICLEI and Covenant of Mayors were not involved.

from the UK¹³ (where the movement started and where Transition Network is based).

The group diversity was considered by participants both as positive and insufficient. Both these answers came to the question "What surprised you?":

"I thought there will be a more "diverse" public" versus "The group diversity and the willingness to deep talk and listen from the great majority of the participants".

As previously underlined, networking was globally one of the most valued aspects in the event:

"Meeting many wonderful people and hearing about their stories and work" (...).

Nevertheless, participants signaled several absent groups, including "victims" and the "unprivileged":

"The relative absence of "POC", given the ethnic diversity of Brussels", "the young, the old, the non-white, the unseen and unheard, the ones truly connected to nature, the ones who are truly shaping a radically new future, the ones who acknowledge the importance of the emotional", "organizations and networks with more resources and 'power'", "people from different class and races, and since we spoke a lot about them, refugees."

In general, we might conclude that all the critical actor roles in sustainability initiatives (Hauck et al., 2020) were present, namely catalysts, intermediaries, frontrunners, drivers and visionaries.

We can also see from the expectations mentioned (and the committed participation in the process) that, for the great majority of the participants, sharing knowledge was the main motivation. This is in fact the cornerstone for a process like this. A precondition for success is to consider knowledge as a public good, leading people to share it because it is the 'right thing to do', i.e., from community interest rather than self-interest (McLure Wasko & Faraj, 2000). When asked how he was expecting to benefit from the process, a participant answered:

"by having a planet safer - by supporting and benefiting of the caring".

In a short sentence: the 'right' people, with the 'right' disposition.

¹³ This can be a curious fact taking into consideration that the United Kingdom's withdrawal from European Union ('Brexit') had just taken place ("A huge sadness as I felt very European just as we are planning to leave...").

How did it go?

We will now focus on the process dynamics.

The aim

Our second assessment criterion (Table 1, page 17) questions if the process “is driven by a purpose and task that are real, practical, and shared by the group”.

We can easily argue that the inquiry question - “How can we better support people to co-create and sustain ambitious and inclusive responses to the climate and ecological crisis at a municipal scale?” – expresses a real and practical purpose. One of the intentions was to support emergence, so no fixed ‘goals’ or ‘tasks’ were set ahead of the event. Nevertheless, the purpose and intentions were specified and widely shared before and during the event (*Dive Deep & Dream Big*, 2019):

“We want to work skilfully and creatively with what emerges rather than drive ourselves towards predetermined outputs and outcomes. However, we are seeking to achieve the following by March¹⁴ 2020:

- *Relevant models, resources and good practice will have been mapped and shared before, during and immediately after the deep dive event; motivating, supporting and constructively challenging local politicians, officials and citizens to move from climate emergency declarations and other statements of intent to designing and implementing meaningful next steps towards one tonne living;*
- *The design of our interactive and experiential deep dive process will have been tested and shared ready to be adjusted and replicated with new actors in different contexts; and*
- *Proposals for more structured collaborative interventions capable of catalysing and supporting ambitious and inclusive systemic change at the municipal scale will be under development with, and for, potential funders.”*

Was this clear enough and ‘shared by the group’? During the event, several aspects were questioned (and partially debated) relating who is “we” or what is the “municipal scale”. Also, some proposals were offered to introduce changes:

“The inflexibility of the inquiry question - the question itself did not seem to be 'on the table' for the conference and although changes to it were suggested, they were never

¹⁴ Postponed to July.

incorporated. Similarly, it never became an option that we could try to answer more than one question, as a whole group.”¹⁵

We might conclude that the shared ownership of the purpose could have been more deeply supported. But, as we will discuss in the following topic, cocreation was fully endorsed.

Cocreation

This third process criterion (Table 1, page 17) asks if the process was “self-organizing, allowing participants to decide on ground rules, objectives, tasks, working groups, and discussion topics”.

One of the manifested intentions of the Dive Deep process was in fact to “foster co-responsibility, sharing power and inviting all participants to help shape both the inquiry process and its outcomes”.

In the beginning of the event, ‘group agreements’ were discussed and settled. Also, participants were allowed to freely join ‘home groups’ with specific tasks like welcoming people, supporting active participation and emotional well-being, timekeeping or maintaining records. The use of ‘open space technology’ (Owen, 2008) allowed participants to decide on topics to be discussed and self-organize workgroups. Right in the beginning, a facilitator reminded that everyone should be “*aware that we might be in a position of structural power and not taking advantage of that*”.

Appreciation for the possibility to jointly construct the process was manifested: “*having a chance to co-develop ideas with others*” was mentioned as one of the highlights. Other participant mentioned that “*this was a live complex democratic action which add rich colour to the reading I have done on deliberative democracy*”.

But inevitably, cocreation is never universally acknowledged:

“I was surprised and found it frustrating when people expressed that subjects they wanted to discuss and questions they wanted to consider weren't present in the room as I felt there was so much possibility to influence the content of the programme. Perhaps it just took people time to settle into that possibility?”¹⁶

The mood

Our fourth criterion (Table 1, page 17) states the importance to engage “participants, keeping them at the table, interested, and learning through in-depth discussion, drama, humor, and informal interaction”.

¹⁵ Included in the response to “What surprised you?” (feedback survey).

¹⁶ idem

It is well established that emotions play a central role in any learning process (Dirkx, 2001). It is argued that “humans react and learn through the lens of emotionally laden experiences” (Shuck, Albornoz, & Winberg, 2007). During the event, several methods and activities were promoted to trigger and hold deep emotions for learning purposes. Apparently three of them caused a great impact¹⁷:

“I didn't have any expectation, so I was surprised. But the food Journey the ceremony and the constellations were truly amazing !!!”, “Food Journey, Ceremony, Constellations!! That so many deep emotions came out in the group”, “my favourite experiences were the food journey and the ceremony” (...)

As presented in the previous chapter (the process), ‘constellations’ made use of psychodrama to explore the ‘stories of our time’. The ‘food journey’ (Mama D, 2017) was the most valued item in the program according to the feedback from participants (Figure 10) and consists of “an animated, immersive, multi-sensory experience of a part of the human journey associated with the movement of food around the planet. It is part live theatre and participatory experiencing; it is part history, science and the socio-economy of food and people” (Sealey-Huggins, 2018). The ceremony was performed as a ritual and explored the landscape of personal renovation.

Other activities played a critical role, like the meditation in day 2, recalling the roots and purpose of our work, the sources of energy and inspiration. Several other informal initiatives were induced, namely coming from the ‘home group’ expected to notice if emotions were “alive in the room and naming/welcoming this”, and “supporting moments and processes for expressing emotions”. These efforts included challenging participants to share their ‘celebrations’ for the planet, for someone else and for themselves (Figure 12).

¹⁷ From the feedback survey.

Figure 12 – Participants were asked to share things they were grateful for.

As mentioned, in the beginning of the event there was a moment to express gratitude for the ones that allowed the group to be together. Exploring humour¹⁸, connecting to positive feelings and honouring the past and future generations was equally encouraged¹⁹, expecting that this could lead to the 'right' mood for the emergence of ideas of possible paths towards transformation.

¹⁸ "The value of humour and the need for time and space to build connections and trust" was a learning expressed by one of the participants, while another mentioned that (s)he "was pleasantly surprised by how much humour translates across languages".

¹⁹ One of the activities included moving around the space and sharing in pairs "something that brought me joy, something that came from older generations and something we want to pass to the future ones".

Apparently, the objective of handling emotions in a good way was achieved, according to many participants that felt nourished by the process:

“Although I had a very challenging and emotional time, I am changed for the better. I found it a really beautiful, moving, supportive experience”, “I was so tired when I arrived, and felt so much better after”, “For me it was a lot of good time”, “spirit of adventure” (...)

For sure, not only ‘positive’ feelings are needed to face the sustainability challenge. Grief for past and future losses of place, species and culture is growing rapidly and needs to be properly accounted for (Cunsolo & Ellis, 2018). This was a topic explored in several workgroup sessions and can embody personal challenges:

“The ritual and more spiritual sides. I believe these have value but since my Catholic childhood I have avoided these. Again the 4th day was difficult as this was completely new to me - I know anger and sadness. but grief I have individually avoided, and I guess been socially shielded from.”

Were these efforts to deal with emotions too intense, taking precious time from other activities? Some participants expressed this view:

“Then Saturday afternoon, to me, was deeply frustrating. Indeed, I nearly decided to go home at that point. I entirely appreciate that there is a need for reflection and if necessary, grief, in events such as this. But if I had known that this event was going to be so dominated by an inner exploration of pain and grief and so on, I would have stayed at home.”, “I thought it would be like a deep and rich exploration of that space where Transition meets municipalities, exploring how to shape policy, how to bring new economic thinking, new democracy models, etc etc. What I ended up with felt like a 3 day grief workshop with a useful half a day of Open Space on the end. While I don’t for a moment want to suggest that such things have no place in Transition, it wasn’t what I was expecting, nor what I feel we really need right now”.

Content

Following our evaluation framework (Table 1, page 17), we ask if the process “encourages challenges to the *status quo* and fosters creative thinking”. We can conclude that this criterion was met, since all the process is meant to create change. Facilitation included several methods, like the iceberg model, to discuss change at a deep level. Participants were challenged to be creative, namely in their presentations, using body language and non-verbal communication.

We also ask if the process “incorporates high-quality information of many types and assures agreement on its meaning” (Table 1, page 17). Previously we discussed how emotions were deeply explored. Here, we try to consider if other sources of information were equally deepened, namely if debates were properly informed from ongoing research on sustainability transitions (Köhler et al., 2019), transformation (Fazey et al., 2018), root causes (Michael Narberhaus & Sheppard, 2015, p. 24) or systems practice (Ison, 2017).

One of the manifested intentions of the Dive Deep process was “to rigorously ground our inquiry in an understanding of the scale and types of change needed to return consumption within planetary boundaries and meet the diverse challenges of the coming decades” (*Dive Deep & Dream Big*, 2019). Looking at the inquiry process, we can conclude that formal moments for discussing knowledge about these topics was rare, and almost reduced to limited exchange between participants.

One of the participants felt challenged by this lack of content, questioning:

“Where were the guest presenters from outside the Transition movement who had things to offer to this question? Where were the real-life case studies of what this is already looking like in many places? Where were the presentations from people in municipalities about how they like to be approached, how it feels from their perspective, how we could help address their challenges? Where were the Transitioners sharing their stories about doing this work?”

The small content that was shared was appreciated for some participants as quite positive²⁰:

“Getting meta understanding on the transition movement (resilience cycle, iceberg model...)”.

According to the feedback from participants, the reduced exploration of content was below expectations and led to the already mentioned polarization that will be discussed in the following topic.

The explosion

The final process-related criterion (Table 1, page 17), is about seeking “consensus only after discussions have fully explored the issues and interests and significant effort has been made to find creative responses to differences”.

As mentioned in the previous chapter (page 28), a polarization emerged on day 4, relating needs for deeper emotional work *versus* more time

²⁰ Included in the response to “What went well for you?” (feedback survey). Only 22% of the participants mentioned knowledge/insights in their responses.

dedicated to content and pathways. Facilitation efforts allowed these differences to become visible and be heard:

“I thought the steering of the process explosion was great. I managed to really let myself be held and relax into the process. I trusted the facilitation team greatly”.

We argue that this was a critical turning point in the process. It was an intense discussion, with strong (and sometimes negative) feelings being manifested and only partial catharsis. It gave visibility to differences that are deeply rooted and most often unseen. It showed how trauma and grief, relating topics as patriarchy, colonization and (intergenerational) climate injustice need to be accounted for.

Climate change (and the ecological crisis) might be considered most of all an ethical challenge coming from a “perfect moral storm” that makes us extremely vulnerable to moral corruption (Gardiner, 2006). Without addressing the large issues of inequality, we are not able to solve policy gridlocks. Before looking ahead, we are asked to look back (Roberts & Parks, 2006, p. 213).

At this stage, the inquiry process reached a crossroad. After the council, where polarization was visible, the group moved to the ‘open space’ without significant efforts being done from the facilitation to explore differences, promote conciliation, integration or some kind of convergence of sensibilities. Nor “to find creative responses to differences”. As expressed from one of the participants:

“I felt that the way I expressed myself at this session was inaccurate and more an emotional reaction, which it would have been good to explore with others so that we could have communicated more clearly, but again - this session was very constrained by time and I think partly as a result, it became more like a theatrical performance in which the objections and strong feelings that were raised by some, were transformed into a sort of tableau and then the conference moved on. It felt like these questions were vying for space at a table where the main event had already been decided and that it was not to be displaced.”

As a consequence, there was somehow a cleavage between ‘heart’ and ‘head/hands’²¹ that persisted until the end of the event. Possibly a lost opportunity to discuss content related to the ethical challenge and look for practical answers to go beyond it, appropriately embracing the emotional aspects (some ideas will be discussed in the topic Pathways on page 47).

²¹ The Head, Heart, Hands principles (HHH) were adopted by the Transition Movement (Hopkins & Thomas, 2016, p. 9; Rusman, 2012, p. 36) and respectively correspond to the ideas of acting on the basis of the best information available, taking care of relationships and emotions and looking for tangible results.

Nevertheless, the “explosion” (as it was named) brought useful *“insights into the range of ‘realities’ we are working with - they all have validity even if they are at times different and can sometimes put you at odds with each other (and sometimes at odds with oneself!)”*.

Or, as expressed yet by another participant, *“I thought we’ll be more in building a new world than grieving the old one, but I think this step was needed. It was very interesting to me to be part of this experience. And I took lots of notes and ideas to work on for my job”*.

Coronavirus

The Dive Deep process needed to race against the COVID-19 outbreak. A few days after the event, most of the European countries were in lockdown (Dunford et al., 2020). It impacted who was present and had many other side effects (like the need for several precautionary measures). Participants from Italy and others had to leave earlier. Some participants voluntarily set themselves temporarily apart from the group, due to light symptoms. Curiously enough, the impact of coronavirus was not integrated into the discussion.

The ‘explosion’ (previous topic) happened on the morning of day 4. Just after some participants had to leave and others were reintegrated. Was the explosion influenced by the coronavirus? One of the participants shared after the event that *“the coronavirus has succeeded for the time being in re-establishing the border between ‘I’ and ‘not-I’”*. We can speculate that this augmented separation fuelled the polarization. Possibly the (hidden) fear increased the urgency to get results (and go home), putting the stakes higher. One of the participants mentioned the surprise *“that people were so negative on the 4th day. I think perhaps there was an overestimation of what we could achieve”*.

What was accomplished?

In this section we present results according to the outcome criteria (Table 1, page 17). This relates to our third research question.

Narrative of change

The first outcome criterion relates the production of a “high-quality agreement”. Agreement on what? We can argue that the Dive Deep goal was mainly to collectively develop a new narrative of change. Narratives of change can be defined as “sets of ideas, concepts, metaphors, discourses or story-lines about change and innovation” (Julia M. Wittmayer et al., 2015).

In the 5 days meeting the group produced a reasonable amount of reflection on “why does the world have to change (rationale)”, “who are the relevant actors (actors)” and “how is the desired future achieved (plot)” (J.M. Wittmayer et al., 2019). However, it did not reach a formal agreement on these issues. The divergent thinking was not followed by convergent thinking, bringing in the risk of reckless change (Cropley, 2006). As one participant put it, summarizing the experience²²:

“Multiple ideas needing clarification & synthesis”.

²² Evaluation form.

We might imagine how this agreement could have looked like, putting the 'pieces of the puzzle'²³ together:

We seem many stories unfolding in our times. Some leading to renewal, with the emergence of a system without politicians, towards collective and self-governance, truly embodying nature. We see actors trapped in their roles and activists' contortions to escape from the sustainability bargain. We suffer with recurrent dynamics of extraction, oppression, and control, leading to despair, grief and breakdown. We feel stretched and want to go deeper, deeper, deeper in our analyses, allowing us to move to a regenerating system.

We place ourselves in the border of inner and outer transition. We know we need to integrate self-care, community care and global care. We need to be conscious of (shadow) archetypes and touch the pain of our culture. Cultural shift is our leverage point and we need to develop playful answers and positive futures. By using collective intelligence and cross-sector participation, alongside humor and silliness, we can break preconceived ideas, prototype regeneration and re-imagine municipalities. By balancing power and addressing privilege, we can curate places of inclusion and connection that take advantage of edges and lead to participatory governance.

We need to move skillfully across scales, from individuals, neighborhoods, municipalities, bioregions, nations, and the planet. We need mapping processes, appropriate frameworks, and a diversity of paradigms. We already have many tools on the shelf. However, we need action and practicalities that move away from patterns of domination and face the real emergency. We need safe zones for expression, bringing in memories from the elders and longings for the desired futures. We need to understand each other and connect our polarities.

²³ Insights collected from the workgroups and participants, in an integration effort performed by the author of the report.

How would we assess the quality of this ‘synthesized’ agreement? We can evaluate it as high taking into consideration that it integrates “the unique knowledge offered by each stakeholder, not only about their interests, but also about aspects of the problem they understand better than anyone else” (Innes & Booher, 1999). These agreements might “be more durable and implementable because, having taken more interests into account, they are less likely to produce unhappy stakeholders who might sabotage implementation”; they are also “more likely not only to be fair, but also to be regarded as fair” (*idem*).

How this narrative of change compares to others coming from social innovation initiatives? We see commonalities like the “high appreciation of communal and relational values” and an “holistic view of the human being” (J.M. Wittmayer et al., 2019). As a distinguishing element, we see that it does not focus in “alternative economic arrangements that question the current neoliberal market economy” (*idem*), at least not explicitly. In fact, this topic has not been discussed many times. There is great proximity with the learnings from the Collective Psychology Project (Evans, 2019).

Fractality

Was this process able to end stalemate²⁴? We argue that the polarization that was reached, and the difficulty to create informed consensus and convergence, is a pattern easily recognizable in our present times. It is visible in the many existent stalemates and gridlocks that prevent significant climate action. This polarization was possibly fueled by the predominance of an intersectional approach, with a strong focus on power and privilege, possibly leading to divisiveness (Micha Narberhaus, 2018).

Processes like the Dive Deep are expected to produce creative ideas, as result of dynamic group discussion (Innes & Booher, 1999). Assessing creativity should involve considering novelty and usefulness (Sarkar & Chakrabarti, 2011), which for sure is not easy, especially in a complex context like this. We can consider that some of the ideas generated are ‘out the box’, probably as a consequence of systemically asking ‘what if’ questions (Hopkins, 2019a). However, we might also consider that the shortage of knowledge (content) and convergent thinking prevented the most creative ideas to come up (Cropley, 2006).

As shared by one of the participants, maybe what worked better in the meeting, was to give light to what is not working. Therefore confronting “real world challenges”²⁵.

²⁴ The second outcome-related criterion in our evaluation (Table 1, page 20).

²⁵ Highlighted by another participant.

Social learning

Social learning can be considered as a collective process by which “actors develop shared meanings, values and understandings through interaction, which provides the basis for joint future action” (Bos, Brown, & Farrelly, 2013).

We can consider that the Dive Deep process was effectively a social learning process, in which participants explored the stories of our times and discussed possibilities, cocreating knowledge. The polarization that occurred was one element that contributed to the learning process, leading to a shared understanding of the (emotional) barriers that might be blocking real transformation. We can therefore expect “results in learning and change in and beyond the group”²⁶. As one participant put it:

“The conviviality, the excellent moderation, the great food, the time and space to bring in the unexpected and often the uncomfortable. That's how we promote real change.”

To further lead to enduring change, nourishing the connections that were created might be crucial. Social (and political) capital²⁷ can be the cornerstone for adaptive governance, nurturing renewal in times of reorganization (Folke et al., 2005). The Dive Deep process provided an arena where social capital was enhanced – when asked to summarize the experience, most of the words shared by participants related to connections – and it is expected to further foster (in)formal collaboration networks.

Pathways

As previously discussed, (until now) no clear agreements were reached relating “proposals for more structured collaborative interventions capable of catalysing and supporting ambitious and inclusive systemic change at the municipal scale” (*Dive Deep & Dream Big*, 2019).

Once more, we can make efforts to put the ‘pieces of the puzzle’ together, imagining what a proposal for a “structured collaborative intervention” could look like, one that could translate the narrative of change²⁸ into action (Figure 13).

²⁶ Another criterion in the evaluation (Table 1, page 20).

²⁷ *Idem*.

²⁸ See page 46.

Figure 13 – A model for a structured collaborative intervention capable of catalysing and supporting ambitious and inclusive systemic change at the municipal scale, based on the topics discussed in the Dive Deep event. It connects dimensions of inner and outer transition, moving (vertically) from the individual to the collective level, and (horizontally) from domination to imagination.

Such an intervention could start by assisting change makers with the needed resources, including time for reflection, connection with nature and true self, finance and peer support, acknowledging that different individuals have different needs. Trauma and grief need to be appropriately handled, facing ethical and psychological aspects and issues of power and culture, making visible the patterns of domination still present, away from moral certainties and with conciliatory efforts. This step should allow the individuals and collectives to enter a safe place where creativity can be allowed to run wild, creating new narratives and experiencing a desired future. Finally, we can bring strategies, models and tools to support inclusive collaboration and collective intelligence, balancing power and facilitating networks able to map and jointly navigate transformation.

Having a clear and agreed framework for an intervention, and a strategy to deliver it, can set “in motion a cascade of changes in attitudes, behaviors and actions, spinoff partnerships, and new practices or institutions”, resulting “in institutions and practices that are flexible and networked, permitting the community to be more creatively responsive to change and conflict” (Innes & Booher, 1999). New ways of doing, organising, framing and/or knowing, as expressed in the theory of Transformative Social Innovation (Haxeltine et al., 2016).

The Dive Deep process should be able to produce “information that stakeholders understand and accept”²⁹, relating the framework for a structured collaborative intervention. Other possibility is to accept the diversity of paradigms, and focus on mapping “relevant models, resources and good practices”. One of the participants shared that:

“What surprised me most is that maybe there isn't much deeper to go as such. Maybe deeper is local? I feel like the event confirmed that we already have most of the tools and processes we need, and the key thing is to share progress and challenges within a wider pool of support.”

²⁹ Criterion in the evaluation (Table 1, page 17).

Discussion

What could be improved?

In this section we discuss how could the process be improved to maximize results. In fact, one of the manifested expectations was to ensure that “the design of our interactive and experiential deep dive process will have been tested and shared ready to be adjusted and replicated with new actors in different contexts” (*Dive Deep & Dream Big*, 2019).

Before

We are not in position to evaluate the effort put in actively involving different people and organizations. We know that a relatively big number was initially assembled, and that many participated in the event. We also know that it was frustrating (for the coordination) that most of them did not involve themselves actively in the preparation. We guess that more clarity on the budget, including earlier decisions, might (partially) have prevented this to happen. We acknowledge that significant personal efforts were made to be involved, but overwork and burnout sabotaged them. Delivery times were often compromised. We saw a complex process being developed with a great dose of passion and voluntarism, adding to undeniable skills.

Some participants mentioned not having enough information:

“I was also surprise at the lack of information in advance. I really had no idea what I was coming to and I think more structure in advance would have set the scene for a more productive time together.”

Still in day 4, participants were questioning “*should we unpack the concepts in the inquiry, like the scale, the inclusivity, the cocreation? Should we reframe the question?*”. We also mentioned that a lack of content was felt by many (page 40).

Possibly, a pre-event webinar series could have been useful to discuss the concepts, to explore the challenges, to get inspiration from experts and practitioners, to create a shared language, to arrive in a more consensual inquiry question. For example, it has already been observed that there is a challenge “in more effectively connecting local, grassroots innovation capacity with the global parameters set by planetary boundaries” (Leach et al., 2012).

Or maybe, what was needed in advance, was deep emotional work (see next topic).

Sensing

The so called ‘explosion’ (page 41) allowed to illuminate our ‘blind spot’, “the inner place or source from which a person or a social system operates” (Scharmer, 2009, p. 22). It revealed how stretched we are between our (personal and collective) traumas and deep emotions of grief, begging for

deep attention and healing, and the need to rush for urgent action to face the (climate) crisis, away from moralities and set to work.

We might consider that the 'explosion' came late (day 4). When we already passed the bottom of the U ('presencing') and were trying to surface on the other side. The facilitation team had already challenged participants many times - "Is there anything I have noticed but not said, in myself or in the wider group, that I can share to support my own or the shared process?" - sensing that something crucial was missing. Finally, it came and was flawlessly handled at that moment.

What could be the most appropriate thing to do next? This 'explosion' demanded the group to bounce back to 'sensing' (Figure 3, page 12), making full sense of what happened, and, most of all, the possibilities. It asked for a conciliation that could bring in a shared will for finding integral pathways able to deal with trauma and work with content that could lead to action.

Unfortunately, we believe, this did not happen³⁰. The group was rushed to enter the 'open spaces' and 'forced' to stay in the cocreation mood. The inevitable happened: the group split in two and no convergent thinking occurred, preventing the participants to fully embrace the complexity of the challenge. This was symptomatic of current polarization, sometimes fueled by social movements (Micha Narberhaus, 2018).

We give the floor to participants:

"A polarity between 'action' and 'feeling', or 'planning' and 'trauma work', or whatever emerged, which I do think could have been identified early on, by me too (especially as it often does come up). The planning of the conference perhaps could have favored a more complex response to this, trying to move it beyond polarity and beyond the adoption of small bits of one approach into a space designed for the dominant 'action' mindset.... Personally, I didn't manage to do this, I felt exhausted and confused before I saw clearly what was happening and then I feel I increased polarization by speaking strongly from a place of emotion. But I would love to think about how a conference could be designed to enable a much more complex sort of shared learning that doesn't shut down or accentuate / create polarity."

"There was most certainly significant "polarity" in the event, as observed or elided to from both ends of the poles over our time together - at least that's how I saw it. That's not a

³⁰ Possibly because it was too sudden and unexpected, or there was a strong will in the organization to keep in track with the planning and the tight schedule, or still (part of the) facilitation was not neutral and was locked in entrenched positions.

bad thing, nor are the individuals who occupied different places on that continuum.

As participants, we just didn't coalesce or come together due to the enormity of our differences in perception as to the nature of our mutual goal. This wasn't the fault of the imaginers of the process, or the facilitators, that's just where we got to. I suspect this was not a product of our specific event but more a result of our gathering being a reflection of our current system, as embodied by us all.

If there is healing and integration to take place - which is not in any way a given - I suspect it would have to take place through a process of individual completion and integration as a first step to then accompanying and inviting and join with whoever we can reach with our calls. I'm sure that for some people at this event that healing process was present. It was for me.

This will be too much hocus pocus for many at the event, an irrelevance alongside the urgency of doing the practical stuff at a municipal level. Yet that practical stuff is such small beer against the enormity of the challenges we face - evidence of which assails us every day should we care to look."

Going deeper

In the U Theory, the first stages of co-initiating and co-sensing are intended to open the mind and heart, in order to be fully aware of past patterns. In the Dive Deep they were both performed in the first day (see Figure 3, page 23), which probably was not enough time. Critical tools like the 'iceberg model' and 'four quadrants' were presented but not meaningfully used.

The 'constellations' allowed an emotional dive, but personal reflections were not fully explored³¹. A participant suggested a 'truth mandala'³² for this purpose. One of these actions, if fully explored, could have brought light to the 'blind spot' sooner.

³¹ "How does one engage with existing narratives of power, especially that located within persons? How does one challenge this using facilitation?" (questioned by one of the participants).

³² The 'Truth Mandala' (Macy & Brown, 2014, p. 119) is an exercise in which participants explore and express pain for the world.

Converging

The biggest challenge for one of the participants was *“the difficulty in thinking together from a middle point of assumptions. For three days I felt like I was drifting from ethereal conversation to yet another purple haze”*. This was already discussed (fractality, page 46) and here we want to point to a possible different path.

Possibly, a (wasted) critical moment for converging happened on day 3. After lunch, each group presented their work and connections between themes were briefly discussed. This could have been a lost opportunity to fully account differences and the complexity of the inquiry, looking for bridges. On the contrary, not enough time was dedicated to this discussion and themes (Figure 7, page 27) were kept siloed in the agenda, competing for attention. On the morning of day 4, the process ‘exploded’.

For sure, many of the participants were able to do this integration by themselves and cross-fertilization happened. One participant celebrated *“the possibility to include deeper truth and feelings with action”*.

Harvesting

Harvesting group discussions was mostly left to their own self-organized responsibility, with intended support from a resourceless ‘home group’. The lack of an efficient harvesting process was evident in day 5, when there was no clarity about ‘open space’ discussions going on.

Some similar events use teams of rapporteurs with the important task of objectively recording discussions, focusing on main points, and looking for connections. This is sometimes complemented by visual harvesting. Again, a better harvesting process could have allowed to give a faster visibility to differences and facilitate converging.

What are the next steps?

Here we explore possibilities for next steps. The Dive Deep process have been apparently closed, opening doors for future initiatives.

From what have been said before, it should be clear that (1) a lot has already been accomplished, and (2) there is an on-going and unfinished work to do.

Benchmarking

A final question comes from our evaluation framework (Table 1, page 16): does Dive Deep compares favorably with other planning methods in terms of costs and benefits?

For sure, we do not even dare to face the enormity and complexity of the question. But we can (should) look at other initiatives with similar bridging goals in order to find similarities and differences, assumingly in a brief and explorative approach. We focus on the three aims relating mapping, replicability and agreement (page 36), and on the cocreation component.

Relating mapping, the 'Municipalities in Transition' project mapped and analyzed 71 cases of local, collaborative transformation happening in 16 countries (Macedo, Huertas, et al., 2020). The European funded 'UrbanA' project created a wiki database of approaches, initiatives and people involved in creating sustainable and just cities³³. These are longer projects with much bigger budgets. 'Municipalities in Transition' produced a clear framework to navigate transformation and tested it in 6 pilots until now. It was developed internally, based on previous experiences. UrbanA intends to focus on policy insights, coming from four co-creative spaces ('arenas'). Other initiatives like the Collective Psychology Project³⁴ used around 200 structured interviews and convenings with experts, activists and policymakers to prepare their clear framework based on 3 transitions (Evans, 2019). The 'Transition Now' initiative³⁵ mobilized mainly grassroots initiatives in 8 events and produced a manifesto supported by a joint reflexion with policymakers ('Agora Politique'). The 'Go Deep' initiative³⁶ was set as an experimental process, tested in 4 communities by a diverse group of organizations, that developed a methodology ('game') and a network of trained facilitators for replication.

The Dive Deep compares favourably in terms of the capacity to congregate different actors, still lacking contributions from policymakers. Mapping was comparably inconsequential, and it yet requires clear agreements and proposals for action.

³³ <https://wiki.urban-arena.eu/>

³⁴ <https://www.collectivepsychology.org/>

³⁵ <https://www.transitionnow.be>

³⁶ <https://godeeproject.org>

Community

Many of the participants manifested the intention to keep contacts alive. This can be supported in many ways, by means of new (online) gatherings or social networks. A community of practice might emerge, or possible existent ones could be potentiated (like the one that is being facilitated in the Municipalities in Transition project³⁷).

There is (was) the intention to keep collecting stories of change.

Crystallizing

It is not too late for conciliation.

We can argue that the process is still in the bottom of the U³⁸, 'presencing' opportunities. According to the Theory U, 'presencing' is the 'one' thing to achieve to support a profound change in people, organizations, and society. 'Presencing'³⁹ is about "operating from the future as it emerges", meaning "to sense, tune in, and act from one's highest future potential – the future that depends on us to bring it into being" (Scharmer, 2009, p. 8). As previously argued, in the Dive Deep process we had a brief glimpse of this possible future, translated into the narrative of change, but we are letting it escape (until now).

Going up the U means to clarify vision and intention from our highest future possibility, in a process called 'crystallizing' (Scharmer, 2009, p. 192). A proposal for a new narrative of change and a model for a structured collaborative intervention have already been presented in this document (pages 45 and 48) and should be discussed and agreed on.

For this discussion, which involves conciliation, all the Dive Deep participants can be called for. Or maybe a subgroup, like the facilitation team – this core group, with its diversity and container, can be a vehicle for the whole to manifest.

It is not an easy task, and convergent thinking is (almost) never as fun as divergent (Akbari Chermahini & Hommel, 2012). Resistance of thought, emotion, and will is to be expected. But this (sub)group has the capacity and the possibility to prototype the new, exploring the future by doing.

Meanwhile the Transition Network started an evaluation process⁴⁰ that includes "co-creating a new, updated narrative about the Transition movement to celebrate and demonstrate the potential of our approach and influence others to get involved, support us and dismantle the barriers we face". Learnings from the Dive Deep will hopefully be taken into the process.

³⁷ This possibility was included in a list of "next steps" prepared by the 'change pirates' group.

³⁸ See sensing, page **Erro! Marcador não definido**.49.

³⁹ Blending of the words "presence" and "sensing".

⁴⁰ <https://transitionnetwork.org/news-and-blog/help-us-to-evaluate-the-transition-movement/>

Co-evolving

Co-evolving is the final movement of the U (Figure 3, page 23), helping to interweave and link the process with the larger ecosystem around. Quite often, is a missing step: “we know about many episodes and stories of great transformational change and breakthrough. But at the end of day they remain merely that: episodes” (Scharmer, 2009, p. 425).

Many possibilities and strategies exist to scale out, up and deep (Moore et al., 2015). The Dive Deep process can try to impact greater numbers by replicating elsewhere⁴¹, using the learnings from the existent process. Possibly, a guide on how to perform a Dive Deep process in our communities can be prepared and shared, or some training delivered.

Besides scaling out, we might try to scale up by impacting law, policy and other institutions. With the support of policy makers, an advocacy team can be set up. According to planning, the Dive Deep learnings should be appropriately translated and delivered to the funder(s), in order to influence future decisions.

Scaling deep is about impacting cultural roots. In our opinion, the need for a cultural shift to leverage change was evident, and the Dive Deep ‘message’ of conciliating trauma and planning, inner and outer transition (page 45), is a valuable one. To spread this idea, an appealing story or narrative and an effective strategy can be prepared, making good use of partners involved, existent networks and communities of practice.

⁴¹ Intentions for this already manifested. A participant also referred the will “to attend a second meeting, which builds upon the lessons learned during this one”.

Conclusions

The 'Dive Deep & Dream Big' process was set as a collaborative inquiry with the question: "How can we better support people to co-create and sustain ambitious and inclusive responses to the climate and ecological crisis at a municipal scale?" (*Dive Deep & Dream Big*, 2019).

To answer this question, a model for a structured collaborative intervention was developed, connecting dimensions of inner and outer transition, moving from the individual to the collective level, and from domination to imagination. This approach (Figure 14) accommodates the integral support of change makers; the exploration of trauma and grief to allow reconciliation; the exercise of wild creativity to create memories from the future; and the intensification of collaboration in the process of navigating transformation. It honours the *motto*: diving deep and dreaming big.

Figure 14 – The schematic answer to the 'Dive Deep & dream Big' inquiry question: "How can we better support people to co-create and sustain ambitious and inclusive responses to the climate and ecological crisis at a municipal scale?"

The research focused on results coming from the Dive Deep process and how they might contribute to catalyse society-wide transformation. We consider as first order effects, already visible and a direct consequence of the process:

- Creation of a social learning environment, that gave visibility to barriers that prevent effective action by fractally reproducing patterns of polarization;
- Enhancement of social and political capital, namely improving connections and the capacity to work together;
- Agreeing on the building blocks of a new narrative of change (page 45), based on reconciliation and still in need of crystallizing.

Potential second order effects, still manifesting and possibly moving beyond the borders of the process:

- Setting of a model for a structured collaborative intervention at municipal level (page 48), allowing to move from domination to imagination, effectively supporting change makers at individual and collective level;
- New partnerships and joint initiatives, pooling resources;
- Expanding the knowledge into the community, supporting replication of the inquiry with improved skills to go deep regarding emotional shifts as well as including systemic analysis, properly addressing polarities;
- Effective advocacy, influencing policies and funding.

As third order effects, that might emerge and get evident in the long run:

- New institutions, including new practices and discourses.

Together these results are expected to renew relations, create a shared sense of meaning and build supportive and resilient contexts for collective action, integrating local mechanisms for deepening and translocal mechanisms of expanding (Avelino, Dumitru, Cipolla, Kunze, & Wittmayer, 2019). What we may call deep glocal governance.

Epilogue

Maybe, as one participant put it, *“we dived deep, but we dreamt not enough”*. But possibly it was better like that because coronavirus would in any case frustrate any immediate expectations. It was one of the last legal ‘hugging’ event to take place in near future and it surely prepared us better for what was to come. Now change is unfolding, opening doors for a paradigm shift and soon the perfect time will come for a sequel. Even if the answer is accepting complexity and no control, we can still find collective strategies to navigate this time together.

The Dive Deep process strongly resonated in me, so together with other participant, Sara Silva, and also Luis Pereira, we decided to experiment with this new structured collaborative intervention (prototyping the new as suggested by Theory U, combining head, heart and hands). We organized a in person two days’ workshop in Lisbon in the beginning of October, integrated in Umundu Lx (a collective festival for sustainable transformation). Taking in expertise from several initiatives, like the Awakened Life Project, Municipalities in Transition and Pop-Up tomorrow, we went through a journey of transcendence, imagination and action. The Dream is alive.

**emotions, learning,
meeting : now act***

*Dive Deep participant [evaluating the event in 5 words]

References

- 8 Shields Institute. (2020). 8 Shields. Retrieved April 16, 2020, from <http://8shields.org/>
- Agyeman, J., Bullard, R. D., & Evans, B. (2002). Exploring the Nexus: Bringing Together Sustainability, Environmental Justice and Equity. *Space and Polity*, 6(1), 77–90. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13562570220137907>
- Akbari Chermahini, S., & Hommel, B. (2012). Creative mood swings: divergent and convergent thinking affect mood in opposite ways. *Psychological Research*, 76(5), 634–640. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00426-011-0358-z>
- Amundsen, H., Hovelsrud, G. K., Aall, C., Karlsson, M., & Westskog, H. (2018). Local governments as drivers for societal transformation: towards the 1.5 °C ambition. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 31, 23–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2017.12.004>
- Avelino, F. (2019). Time to ignite the power of translocal social movements. *The Broker*. Retrieved from <http://www.thebrokeronline.eu/Blogs/Inclusive-Economy-Europe/Time-to-ignite-the-power-of-translocal-social-movements>
- Avelino, F., Dumitru, A., Cipolla, C., Kunze, I., & Wittmayer, J. (2019). Translocal empowerment in transformative social innovation networks. *European Planning Studies*, 0(0), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09654313.2019.1578339>
- Bendell, J. (2018). Deep Adaptation: A Map for Navigating Climate Tragedy. *IFLAS Occasional Paper*, 2, 1–31. Retrieved from www.iflas.info
- Bennett, E. M., Solan, M., Biggs, R., McPhearson, T., Norström, A. V., Olsson, P., ... Xu, J. (2016). Bright spots: seeds of a good Anthropocene. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 14(8), 441–448. <https://doi.org/10.1002/fee.1309>
- Berkes, F. (2009). Evolution of co-management: Role of knowledge generation, bridging organizations and social learning. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 90(5), 1692–1702. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2008.12.001>
- Bockelbrink, B., Priest, J., & David, L. (2018). Sociocracy 3.0 - A Practical Guide. Retrieved November 22, 2018, from https://sociocracy30.org/_res/practical-guide/S3-practical-guide-ebook.pdf
- Bos, J. J., Brown, R. R., & Farrelly, M. A. (2013). A design framework for creating social learning situations. *Global Environmental Change*, 23(2), 398–412. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2012.12.003>
- Bulkeley, H. (2005). Reconfiguring environmental governance: Towards a politics of scales and networks. *Political Geography*, 24(8), 875–902. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.polgeo.2005.07.002>

- Carothers, T., & O'Donohue, A. (2019). *Democracies Divided: The Global Challenge of Political Polarization*. Washington, USA: Brookings Institution Press.
- Carson, L. (2008). Creating democratic surplus through citizens' assemblies. *Journal of Public Deliberation*, 4(1).
- Cash, D. (2000). Linking global and local scales: designing dynamic assessment and management processes. *Global Environmental Change*, 10(2), 109–120. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-3780\(00\)00017-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0959-3780(00)00017-0)
- Centola, D., Becker, J., Brackbill, D., & Baronchelli, A. (2018). Experimental evidence for tipping points in social convention. *Science*, 360(6393), 1116–1119. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aas8827>
- Climate Chance. (2019). *"Local Action Book": Synthesis Report on Climate Action by Local and Subnational Governments*. Paris, France: Global Observatory on Non-State Climate Action.
- Cropley, A. (2006). In Praise of Convergent Thinking. *Creativity Research Journal*, 18(3), 391–404. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15326934crj1803_13
- Cunsolo, A., & Ellis, N. R. (2018). Ecological grief as a mental health response to climate change-related loss. *Nature Climate Change*, 8(4), 275–281. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0092-2>
- Dardeli, A. (2020). Young people are key to defusing unrest and restoring public trust. Retrieved March 18, 2020, from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2020/03/young-people-key-defusing-unrest/>
- Davey, J., & Ebner, J. (2019). *The Great Replacement: The Violent Consequences of Mainstreamed Extremism*. London, UK: Institute for Strategic Dialogue. Retrieved from <https://www.isdglobal.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/The-Great-Replacement-The-Violent-Consequences-of-Mainstreamed-Extremism-by-ISD.pdf>
- Dirkx, J. M. (2001). The Power of Feelings: Emotion, Imagination, and the Construction of Meaning in Adult Learning. *New Directions for Adult and Continuing Education*, 2001(89), 63. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ace.9>
- Dive Deep & Dream Big*. (2019). Retrieved from <https://www.conferize.com/divedeepdreambig/event>
- Drawdown. (2019). Project Drawdown. Retrieved September 26, 2019, from <https://www.drawdown.org/>
- Dryzek, J. S., Bächtiger, A., & Milewicz, K. (2011). Toward a Deliberative Global Citizens' Assembly. *Global Policy*, 2(1), 33–42. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1758-5899.2010.00052.x>
- Dunford, D., Dale, B., Stylianou, N., Lowther, E., Ahmed, M., & Arenas, I. de la T. (2020). Coronavirus: The world in lockdown in maps and charts. *BBC News*. Retrieved from <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-52103747>

- EEA. (2016). *Urban adaptation to climate change in Europe 2016 - Transforming cities in a changing climate*. Luxembourg: European Environment Agency. <https://doi.org/10.2800/021466>
- Eisenhauer, D. C. (2016). Pathways to Climate Change Adaptation: Making Climate Change Action Political. *Geography Compass*, 10(5), 207–221. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gec3.12263>
- Evans, A. (2019). *A Larger Us*. Collective Psychology Project.
- Extinction Rebellion. (2019). Retrieved September 26, 2019, from <https://rebellion.earth>
- Fazey, I., Moug, P., Allen, S., Beckmann, K., Blackwood, D., Bonaventura, M., ... Wolstenholme, R. (2018). Transformation in a changing climate: a research agenda. *Climate and Development*, 10(3), 197–217. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17565529.2017.1301864>
- Feola, G., & Nunes, R. (2014). Success and failure of grassroots innovations for addressing climate change: The case of the Transition Movement. *Global Environmental Change*, 24(1), 232–250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2013.11.011>
- Foa, R. S., Klassen, A., Slade, M., Rand, A., & Collins, R. (2020). *Global Satisfaction with Democracy 2020*. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Centre for the Future of Democracy. Retrieved from www.bennettinstitute.cam.ac.uk
- Folke, C., Hahn, T., Olsson, P., & Norberg, J. (2005). Adaptive Governance of Social-Ecological Systems. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 30(1), 441–473. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.energy.30.050504.144511>
- Fridays For Future. (n.d.). Retrieved September 26, 2019, from <https://www.fridaysforfuture.org>
- Future Earth. (2019). FutureEarth. Retrieved September 26, 2019, from <https://futureearth.org/>
- Gardiner, S. M. (2006). A Perfect Moral Storm: Climate Change, Intergenerational Ethics and the Problem of Moral Corruption. *Environmental Values*, 15(3), 397–413. <https://doi.org/10.3197/096327106778226293>
- Garmestani, A. S., Allen, C. R., & Cabezas, H. (2008). Panarchy, Adaptive Management and Governance: Policy Options for Building Resilience. *Nebraska Law Review*, 87(4). Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/nlr/vol87/iss4/5>
- Geels, F. W., & Schot, J. (2007). Typology of sociotechnical transition pathways. *Research Policy*, 36(3), 399–417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.respol.2007.01.003>
- Gorissen, L., Spira, F., Meynaerts, E., Valkering, P., & Frantzeskaki, N. (2018). Moving towards systemic change? Investigating acceleration dynamics of urban sustainability transitions in the Belgian City of Genk. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 173, 171–185.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2016.12.052>

- Harari, Y. N. (2016). *Homo Deus: A brief history of tomorrow*. Random House.
- Harari, Y. N. (2018). *21 Lessons for the 21st Century*. Random House.
- Harvey, F. (2019). One climate crisis disaster happening every week. *The Guardian*. Retrieved from <https://www.theguardian.com/environment/2019/jul/07/one-climate-crisis-disaster-happening-every-week-un-warns>
- Hauck, J., Omann, I., Thronicker, I., Spekkink, W., Ayude, A. D., Maricchiolo, F., ... Pandur, V. (2020). *Understanding actor roles in sustainability initiatives : an exploratory study in five European countries* (UFZ Discussion Papers, 2/2020). Leipzig. Retrieved from <https://nbn-resolving.org/urn:nbn:de:0168-ssoar-66850-6>
- Haxeltine, A., Avelino, F., Bonno, P., Dumitru, A., Kemp, R., Longhurst, N., ... Wittmayer, J. M. (2016). *A framework for Transformative Social Innovation (TRANSIT Working Paper # 5)*, TRANSIT: EU SSH.2013.3.2-1 Grant agreement no: 613169. TRANSIT Working Paper #5.
- Hodson, M., & Marvin, S. (2017). Intensifying or transforming sustainable cities? Fragmented logics of urban environmentalism. *Local Environment*, 22(sup1), 8–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2017.1306498>
- Hof, A., Berg, H., Frantzeskaki, N., Holsten, A., Vuuren, D. Van, Maschmayer, S., ... Kropp, J. (2016). *Sustainability Transitions Towards Low-Carbon Societies*. TESS, ARTS & PATHWAYS.
- Hopkins, R. (2019a). *From What Is to What If: Unleashing the Power of Imagination to Create the Future We Want*. London, UK: Chelsea Green Publishing.
- Hopkins, R. (2019b). What if Friday September 20th 2019 was the day the world tipped? Retrieved from <https://www.robhopkins.net/2019/09/23/what-if-friday-september-20th-2019-was-the-day-the-world-tipped/>
- Hopkins, R., & Thomas, M. (2016). *The Essential Guide to Doing Transition*. Totnes: Transition Network.
- Hsieh, H.-F., & Shannon, S. E. (2005). Three Approaches to Qualitative Content Analysis. *Qualitative Health Research*, 15(9), 1277–1288. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732305276687>
- Independent Group of Scientists appointed by the Secretary-General. (2019). *The Future is Now – Science for Achieving Sustainable Development. Global Sustainable Development Report 2019*. New York.
- Innes, J. E., & Booher, D. E. (1999). Consensus building and complex adaptive systems: A framework for evaluating collaborative planning. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 65(4), 412–423. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944369908976071>

- IPCC. (2018). *Global Warming of 1.5°C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change*,. (V. Masson-Delmotte, P. Zhai, H.-O. Pörtner, D. Roberts, J. Skea, P. R. Shukla, ... T. Waterfield, Eds.).
- Ison, R. (2017). *Systems Practice: How to Act: In situations of uncertainty and complexity in a climate-change world* (Second). London: Springer London & The Open University. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4471-7351-9>
- Jorgensen, D. L. (2015). Participant Observation. In *Emerging Trends in the Social and Behavioral Sciences* (Vol. 2014, pp. 1–15). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118900772.etrds0247>
- Kemmis, S., McTaggart, R., & Nixon, R. (2014). *The Action Research Planner: Doing Critical Participatory Action Research*. Singapore: Springer Singapore. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-4560-67-2>
- Köhler, J., Geels, F. W., Kern, F., Markard, J., Onsongo, E., Wieczorek, A., ... Wells, P. (2019). An agenda for sustainability transitions research: State of the art and future directions. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 31, 1–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2019.01.004>
- KR. (2020). *2019 Foundation Annual Report*. Copenhagen, Denmark.
- Lazer, D. M. J., Baum, M. A., Benkler, Y., Berinsky, A. J., Greenhill, K. M., Menczer, F., ... Zittrain, J. L. (2018). The science of fake news. *Science*, 359(6380), 1094–1096. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aao2998>
- Leach, M., Rockström, J., Raskin, P., Scoones, I., Stirling, A. C., Smith, A., ... Olsson, P. (2012). Transforming Innovation for Sustainability. *Ecology and Society*, 17(2), art11. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-04933-170211>
- Lertzman, R. (2015). *Environmental Melancholia: Psychoanalytic dimensions of engagement*. London, UK: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315851853>
- Loorbach, D. A., & Lijnis Huffenreuter, R. (2013). Exploring the economic crisis from a transition management perspective. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 6, 35–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2013.01.003>
- Macedo, P. (2019). *Municipalities in Transition - Deep collaboration between community-based initiatives and local governments*. Porto: Centre for Ecology, Evolution and Environmental Changes, Faculdade de Ciências, Universidade de Lisboa. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3635471>
- Macedo, P. (2020). Bridging in the edge of chaos - Catalysing (trans)local transformative efforts to face the governance challenge. In *Proceedings from the IST2020 - 11th International Sustainability Transitions Conference* (p. 3154). Vienna. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4050270>

- Macedo, P., Huertas, A., Bottone, C., del Río, J., Hillary, N., Brazzini, T., ... Penha-Lopes, G. (2020). Learnings from Local Collaborative Transformations: Setting a Basis for a Sustainability Framework. *Sustainability*, 12(3), 795. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12030795>
- Macedo, P., Santos, F. D., Pedersen, J. T., & Penha-Lopes, G. (2020). Climate action: is coronavirus what we have been waiting for? (and now what?). *Submitted for Publication*, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3753052>
- Macy, J., & Brown, M. Y. (2014). *Coming Back to Life: The Updated Guide to the Work that Reconnects*. Gabriola Island, Canada: New Society Publishers. Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/books?hl=pt-PT&lr=&id=DuH0AgAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&ots=O3KyDkahaG&sig=vL-53HpZT6aYWNwcBR4Npoqt8C8>
- Mama D. (2017). The Food Journey. Retrieved April 23, 2020, from <http://communitycentredknowledge.yolasite.com/>
- McGregor, C., & Crowther, J. (2016). The Transition movement as politics and pedagogy in communities. *Community Development Journal*, 53(1), 8–24. <https://doi.org/10.1093/cdj/bsw024>
- McLure Wasko, M., & Faraj, S. (2000). “It is what one does”: why people participate and help others in electronic communities of practice. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 9(2–3), 155–173. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-8687\(00\)00045-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0963-8687(00)00045-7)
- MiT. (2018). Municipalities in Transition – Exploring how municipalities & citizens can work better together. Retrieved November 20, 2018, from <http://municipalitiesintransition.org/>
- Moore, M.-L., Riddell, D., & Vocisano, D. (2015). Scaling Out, Scaling Up, Scaling Deep: Strategies of Non-profits in Advancing Systemic Social Innovation. *Journal of Corporate Citizenship*, 2015(58), 67–84. <https://doi.org/10.9774/GLEAF.4700.2015.ju.00009>
- Moreno, J. L. (1953). *Who shall survive? Foundations of sociometry, group psychotherapy and socio-drama*. Beacon House.
- Narberhaus, Micha. (2018). *Systemic activism in a polarised world*. Retrieved from <https://www.smart-csos.org/images/Documents/Systemic-Activism-in-a-Polarised-World.pdf>
- Narberhaus, Michael. (2019). *Switching off the autopilot: An evolutionary toolbox for the Great Transition*. Smart CSOs Lab.
- Narberhaus, Michael, & Sheppard, A. (2015). *Re.imagining Activism: a practical guide for the Great Transition*. Smart CSOs Lab.
- O’Brien, K. (2012). Global environmental change II: from adaptation to deliberate transformation. *Progress in Human Geography*, 36(5), 667–676. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309132511425767>
- O’Brien, K. L. (2016). Climate change and social transformations: is it time for a quantum leap? *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*,

- 7(5), 618–626. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.413>
- O’Neill, D. W., Fanning, A. L., Lamb, W. F., & Steinberger, J. K. (2018). A good life for all within planetary boundaries. *Nature Sustainability*, 1(2), 88–95. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0021-4>
- Ostrom, E. (2010). Polycentric systems for coping with collective action and global environmental change. *Global Environmental Change*, 20(4), 550–557. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2010.07.004>
- Owen, H. (2008). *Open space technology: A user’s guide*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Penha-Lopes, G., & Henfrey, T. (2019). *Reshaping the Future: how local communities are catalysing social, economic and ecological transformation in Europe. The First Status Report on Community-led Action on Sustainability and Climate Change in Europe*. Brussels, Belgium: ECOLISE.
- Pinto, M., Macedo, M., Macedo, P., Almeida, C., & Silva, M. (2015). The Lifecycle of a Voluntary Policy Innovation: The Case of Local Agenda 21. *Journal of Management and Sustainability*, 5(2), 69–83. <https://doi.org/10.5539/jms.v5n2p69>
- Raworth, K. (2012). *A safe and just space for humanity: Can we live within the doughnut. Oxfam Policy and Practice: Climate Change and Resilience*. Oxford, UK.
- Reckien, D., Salvia, M., Heidrich, O., Church, J. M., Pietrapertosa, F., De Gregorio-Hurtado, S., ... Dawson, R. (2018). How are cities planning to respond to climate change? Assessment of local climate plans from 885 cities in the EU-28. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 191, 207–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.03.220>
- Reed, B. (2007). Shifting from ‘sustainability’ to regeneration. *Building Research & Information*, 35(6), 674–680. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613210701475753>
- Ripple, W. J., Wolf, C., Newsome, T. M., Barnard, P., & Moomaw, W. R. (2019). World Scientists’ Warning of a Climate Emergency. *BioScience*, 70(1), 100–100. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biz088>
- Roberts, J. T., & Parks, B. (2006). *A climate of injustice: Global inequality, north-south politics, and climate policy*. MIT press.
- Robertson, B. (2015). *Holacracy: The new management system for a rapidly changing world*. New York: Henry Holt and Company. Retrieved from <https://www.google.com/books?hl=pt-PT&lr=&id=PUREBQAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR1&ots=92yr72jbLL&sig=ljiTK9EynJIQrsBxyuOiID0aC6s>
- Rosenbloom, D. (2017). Pathways: An emerging concept for the theory and governance of low-carbon transitions. *Global Environmental Change*, 43, 37–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2016.12.011>
- Ruiz-campillo, X. (2020). Strategies to Mitigate Climate Greenhouse Gas Emissions in Spanish Cities. In *CLIMATE2020 - 7th Climate Change*

Online Conference. Hamburg, Germany: Hamburg University of Applied Sciences.

- Rusman, W. (2012). *How to Involve Citizens in Sustainable Development. An Exploratory Study of the Transition Towns Network in the Netherlands and Freiburg, Germany*. Retrieved from [https://dspace.library.uu.nl/bitstream/handle/1874/252680/Masterthes is Rusman %28SPSI%29.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y](https://dspace.library.uu.nl/bitstream/handle/1874/252680/Masterthes%20SPSI%29.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y)
- Russell, B. (2019). Beyond the Local Trap: New Municipalism and the Rise of the Fearless Cities. *Antipode*, 51(3), 989–1010. <https://doi.org/10.1111/anti.12520>
- Sarkar, P., & Chakrabarti, A. (2011). Assessing design creativity. *Design Studies*, 32(4), 348–383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.destud.2011.01.002>
- Scategni, W. (2005). *Psychodrama, Group Processes and Dreams*. *Psychodrama, Group Processes and Dreams*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203989098>
- Scharmer, C. O. (2009). *Theory U: Learning from the future as it emerges*. San Francisco, California: Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Sealey-Huggins, L. (2018). Embarking on a Food Journey. Retrieved April 23, 2020, from https://warwick.ac.uk/fac/cross_fac/iatl/sharing-practice/blog/2018-06-21/
- Sekulova, F., Anguelovski, I., Argüelles, L., & Conill, J. (2017). A 'fertile soil' for sustainability-related community initiatives: A new analytical framework. *Environment and Planning A*, 49(10), 2362–2382. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0308518X17722167>
- Shove, E. (2010). Beyond the ABC: Climate Change Policy and Theories of Social Change. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 42(6), 1273–1285. <https://doi.org/10.1068/a42282>
- Shuck, B., Albornoz, C., & Winberg, M. (2007). Emotions and Their Effect on Adult Learning : A Constructivist Perspective. In S. M. Nielsen & M. S. Plakhotnik (Eds.), *Proceedings of the Sixth Annual College of Education Research Conference: Urban and International Education Section* (pp. 108–113). Miami: Florida International University. Retrieved from http://coeweb.fiu.edu/research_conference/
- Spradley, J. P. (1980). *Participant observation*. Harcourt Brace Jovanovich College Publishers.
- Strauss, A., & Corbin, J. (1994). Grounded theory methodology. In *Handbook of qualitative research* (pp. 273–285).
- Tellus Institute. (2019). Great Transition Initiative - Toward a transformative vision and praxis. Retrieved September 26, 2019, from <https://greattransition.org/>
- Terry, G. (2009). No climate justice without gender justice: an overview of the issues. *Gender & Development*, 17(1), 5–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13552070802696839>

- Thompson, M. (2020). What's so new about New Municipalism? *Progress in Human Geography*, 38(2007), 030913252090948. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309132520909480>
- Tosun, J., & Schoenefeld, J. J. (2017). Collective climate action and networked climate governance. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 8(1), e440. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.440>
- TRANSIT. (2017). Manifesto for Transformative Social Innovation. Retrieved from <https://tsimanifesto.org/>
- United Nations. (2019). Climate Action Summit Closing Release. Retrieved from https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/assets/pdf/CAS_closing_release.pdf
- Unruh, G. C. (2002). Escaping carbon lock-in. *Energy Policy*, 30(4), 317–325. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-4215\(01\)00098-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0301-4215(01)00098-2)
- van Buuren, A., & Loorbach, D. (2009). Policy innovation in isolation? *Public Management Review*, 11(3), 375–392. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14719030902798289>
- Wilber, K. (2005). Introduction to integral theory and practice. *AQAL Journal of Integral Theory and Practice*, 1(1), 2–38. Retrieved from https://redfrogcoaching.com/uploads/3/4/2/1/34211350/ken_wilber_introduction_to_integral.pdf
- Wittmayer, Julia M., Backhaus, J., Avelino, F., Pel, B., Strasser, T., & Kunze, I. (2015). *Narratives of change: How Social Innovation Initiatives engage with their transformative ambitions*. TRANSIT working paper #4.
- Wittmayer, J.M., Backhaus, J., Avelino, F., Pel, B., Strasser, T., Kunze, I., & Zuijderwijk, L. (2019). Narratives of change: How social innovation initiatives construct societal transformation. *Futures*, 112(June), 102433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.futures.2019.06.005>
- Young, J., Haas, E., & McGown, E. (2008). *Coyote's guide to connecting with nature: For kids of all ages and their mentors*. Wilderness Awareness School.

Annex

Dive Deep participants (Brussels event):

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Lena Abbou

Mama D Ujuaje

Manjola Piniqi

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Muttiah Yoganathan

Nathalie Everard

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